

Smarandache's codification used in computer programming

Since Venn diagram is very hard to draw and to read for the cases when the number of sets becomes big (say $n = 8, 9, 10, 11, \dots$), Smarandache has proposed a generalization of Venn diagram through an *algebraic representation* for the intersection of sets.

Let $n \geq 1$ be the number of sets S_1, S_2, \dots, S_n , that are to be intersected in all possible ways in a Venn diagram. Let $1 \leq k \leq n$ be an integer.

He noted by: $i_1 i_2 \dots i_k$ the Venn diagram region that belongs to the sets S_{i_1} and S_{i_2} and \dots and S_{i_k} only, for all k and all n .

The part which is outside of all sets (i.e. the complement of the union of all sets) is noted by 0 (zero).

Each Venn diagram will have 2^n disjoint parts, and each such disjoint part (except the above part 0) will be formed by combinations of k numbers from the numbers: 1 2 3 \dots n .

Let see an example of **Smarandache's codification**, for $n = 3$, for sets S_1, S_2 , and S_3 .

Therefore, part 12 means that part which belongs to S_1 and S_2 only; part 3 means that part which belongs to S_3 only.

This helps to the construction of a base formed by all these disjoint parts, and implementation in a computer program of each set from the power set $\mathcal{P}(S_1 \cup S_2 \cup \dots \cup S_n)$ by a unique combination of numbers 1, 2, \dots , n .

When $n \geq 10$, one uses one space in between numbers: for example, if we want to represent the disjoint part which is the intersection of S_3, S_{10} , and S_{27} only, he used the notation [3 10 27], with blanks in between set indexes.

Smarandache's codification is user friendly in algebraically doing unions and intersections in a simple way. Union of sets S_a, S_b, \dots, S_v is formed by all disjoint parts that have in their index either the number a , or the number b , \dots , or the number v .

While intersection of S_a, S_b, \dots, S_v is formed by all disjoint parts that have in their index all numbers a, b, \dots, v .

For $n = 3$ and the diagram above:

$S_1 \cup S_{23} = \{1, 12, 13, 23, 123\}$, i.e. all disjoint parts that include in their indexes either the number 1, or the number 23.

$S_1 \cap S_2 = \{12, 123\}$, i.e. all disjoint parts that have in their index the numbers 12.